

An Experimental Study on Partial Replacement of Cement by Using Groundnut Shell Powder in Concrete

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Abstract—Concrete plays a prominent role in the construction industry. In the present situation, there is a deficiency of this material so there is a need to discover alternatives to replace it within the concrete materials. In order to overcome this situation numerous, dissipate items which are freely available like a paper waste, rice husks, maize combs, snail shells, palm-kennel shell, coconut shell, saw dust, groundnut shell etc., can be utilized as the partial replacement. Among all of these, Ground nut shell powder is one of the good waste material available from the oil industry in our region, The ground nut shell contains CaO , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 . This experimental investigation was carried out to assess the quality of concrete in which cement was replaced with ground nut shell. Fresh and Hardened properties were worked out with different replacement levels. In our study the replacement is done at different percentages like 0%, 2.5%, 7.5%, 10% and 12.5% and its impact on properties of concrete was explored by the Compressive Strength, Split Tensile Strength and Flexural Strength. From the previous paper studies, it is observed that the ground nut shell powder can effectively be utilized up to 10% as cement replacement without considerable alter in Strength of concrete.

Keywords— Ground nut shell Powder, Compressive Strength, Flexural Strength, split tensile strength.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Introduction

Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials, but because cement manufacture produces a lot of carbon emissions, its production has a big environmental impact. Researchers have concentrated on employing substitute materials to partially replacement of cement in order to mitigate this problem, lowering its environmental impact while preserving or enhancing the qualities of concrete.

The viability of partially substituting groundnut shell powder (GSP) for cement in concrete is investigated in this study. An agricultural byproduct that is widely accessible and frequently thrown away as waste are groundnut shells. In addition to encouraging sustainable waste management, using them in concrete lessens the need for cement and supports environmentally friendly building methods. The purpose of the experimental study is to assess concrete's mechanical qualities, including tensile strength, flexural strength and compressive strength, by replacing cement with varying proportions of ground nut shell like 0%, 2.5%, 7.5%, 10%, 12.5%. The groundnut shell contains different type of chemicals like CaO , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 .

In addition to lowering costs, using groundnut shell powder in concrete also saves energy and reduces environmental damage. Groundnut shell powders pozzolanic properties are superior. As time increases, so does the pozzolanic activity

of ash, groundnut shell powder may decrease water absorption and drying shrinkage in cement concrete, but also lengthens the setting time. Groundnut shell powder may increase the strength and impermeability of concrete by blocking its natural pore structure. The primary goal is to use groundnut shell powder to find a way to reduce the environmental pollution brought on by the production of cement.

Dr. M. Vijaya Sekhar Reddy, et al (2017) are studied that “Groundnut Shell Ash as partial Replacement of cement in concrete” the study explores the potential of using Groundnut shell Ash (GSA) as a Supplementary cementing material in concrete, the results shown that GSA can be collectively used as a cement replacement up to 10% without significantly affecting the strength of concrete. The GSA made from agricultural waste as replacement of cement to reduce the initial cost. The strengths of cement/Ash concrete increased with curing period but decreased with decreasing ash percentage, the experimental tests are conducted compressive strength and split tensile test and flexural strength. By reducing the GSA content after 10% the strength will be decreases so the optimum percentage by add replacing in concrete is 10% [1].

Mahmoud H. et al. (2012) conducted an inquiry into the fabrication of sand Crete blocks that substitute groundnut shell ash (GSA) for cement. For every replacement level (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 percent), six sand Crete blocks were cast using GSA. On days 7, 14, 21, and 28, the blocks were crushed and cured. According to the findings, the compressive strength falls between 4.50 and 0.26 N/mm². 10% was the ideal replacement level, and the equivalent strength was 3.58 N/mm² [2].

Abdul Wahab Abro et.al (2021) are studied that “An Investigation on Compressive Strength of Concrete Blended with Groundnut Shell Ash” the study explores about the effect of groundnut shell powder as a cement replacement by the 3% to 15% by the weight of cement, with the 3% increment with 1:2:4 binding ratio mixed with 0.5 water/cement ratio. As the result, with the substitution of groundnut shell ash it is decreased as compared with the normal mix. Compressive strength of the groundnut shell ash concrete is increased up to 6% in comparison of control mix. The Additional substitution of binding material with ash of groundnut shell beyond 6%, the compressive strength is decreased than that of normal mix. [3].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Materials

- Cement

Ordinary Portland cement available in the market of 43 grade was used in the project, conforming to the IS: 8112-1989 standards in India. It offers a compressive strength of 43 MPa (megapascals) at 28 days. This cement is made by blending and calcining limestone and clay, producing clinker, then grinding it with gypsum.

Fig. 1. Cement

TABLE I. BASIC CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CEMENT

Sl. No.	Chemical Composition	Percentage (%)
1	Silica	17-25%
2	Alumina	3.0-8%
3	Ferric Oxide	0.5-6%
4	Calcium Oxide	1.3-3%
5	Magnesium Oxide	0.1-4%
6	Sodium Oxide	0.4-1.3%

- Coarse Aggregate

Natural Crushed Stone with 20mm down size was used as coarse aggregate. Coarse Aggregate refers to irregular and granular materials such as sand, gravel, crushed stone are used for making the concrete. We are used 20mm size of coarse aggregate for conventional concrete and mixed concrete.

Fig. 2. Coarse Aggregate

- Fine Aggregate

The fine aggregate of zone II is coarse sand, with a maximum particle size of 4.75 mm and a fineness modulus of 2.2 to 2.6 as per IS Code-383(1970). Fine aggregates are small-sized particles that are commonly used in construction. They are typically made of crushed stone, sand, or crushed slag, and have a diameter of less than 9.5 mm.

Fig. 3. Fine Aggregate

- Groundnut Shell Powder

We have collected the waste material Groundnut shell from the Rayachoty which is near to Kadapa District. First, we have dried the Groundnut Shells then it was powdered in the flour mill. The Groundnut Shell powder contains many chemicals which can be observed for the construction use.

Fig. 4. Groundnut Shell Powder

- Water

In this study, Water is used for mixing and curing the specimens. Water plays an important role in conventional concrete as well as in mixed concrete, and also used in construction.

B. Methodology

- Concrete Mix Design

Mix design of M30 grade is used for the concrete as per IS:10262-2009. The Specimens are prepared for M30 grade of concrete with different percentages of groundnut shell powder. The details of casting and testing of specimen are mentioned below.

TABLE II. MIX PROPORTIONS

Sl. No	Mix	Cement (%)	Groundnut Shell Powder (%)
1	Nominal	100	0
2	Mix-1	97.5	2.5
3	Mix-2	92.5	7.5
4	Mix-3	90	10
5	Mix-4	87.5	12.5

- Casting and Curing

The dimensions of Cubes are 150x150x150mm, cylinders of size 150mm diameter and 300mm height and the bar of size 100x100x500mm. For every mix, the concrete is made and kept for the curing period of 7 days, 14 days and 28 days. For each mix we will prepare 3 cubes, 3 cylinders and 3 bars for the compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength testing.

III. TEST PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

The samples are calculated and tested for compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength. As per IS Code the tests are done. Compressive strength of cubes is tested for 7, 14, and 28 days according to the code of IS 516-1959, Flexural Strength test of beams were tested for 7, 14, and 28 days according to the code of IS 516-1959 and the Tensile strength test of cylinders were tested for 7, 14, and 28 days according to the code of IS 516-1959.

A. Compressive strength

It is the ability of material carries load without any crack on its surface. It reduces the size when the material is under compression, it elongates the size, while it is in tension. The compression strength test is done by using Compressive Testing Machine or Universal Testing Machine. It gives detailed information of concrete characteristics. The tests are done as per the specification of IS 516:1959. Dimensions of concrete cube is 150mm*150mm*150 mm. The rate of 140 kg/cm² per minute applied the load. It depends on various factors such as strength of cement, concrete material quality.

TABLE III. VALUES OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

Sl. No	Mix	Compressive Strength (MPa)		
		7 Days	14 days	28 Days
1	Referenced Concrete	31.35	35.4	38
2	Mix-1	29.65	32.29	35.89
3	Mix-2	26.75	28.63	31.4
4	Mix-3	23.06	25.54	28.01
5	Mix-4	21.57	23.68	25.62

Fig. 5. Compressive Strength for 7 Days, 14 Days and 28 Days

B. Tensile Strength

It resists the tensile stresses without any breaking. Concrete is a durable building material and it is strong, but its tensile strength is less compared to Compressive strength. Tensile strength test is done by using Compressive Testing Machine or Universal Testing Machine. The tensile test is done as per the specification of IS 516:1959. Dimension of cylinder are diameter of 150mm and height of 300mm. The machine applies the loads in between 1.2 – 2.4 MPa/min. The tensile strength concrete is 10 % - 12% of its compressive strength.

TABLE IV. VALUES OF TENSILE STRENGTH

Sl. No	Mix	Tensile Strength (MPa)		
		7 Days	14 days	28 Days
1	Referenced Concrete	4.2	5.33	6.14
2	Mix-1	3.82	4.59	5.67
3	Mix-2	3.47	3.98	4.93
4	Mix-3	3.09	3.27	4.05
5	Mix-4	2.74	2.98	3.57

Fig. 6. Split Tensile Strength for 7 Days, 14 Days and 28 Days

C. Flexural Strength

Flexural test indirectly evaluates the tensile strength concrete Flexural strength test is done by using Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The UTM testing machine can apply various types of loads such as tension, compression, bending, and shear. The flexural test is done as per the specification of IS 516:1959. Dimensions of beam 100mm*100mm*500mm. It applies the load of 400 Kg/min. The flexural strength of concrete is 12% - 20 % of compressive strength.

TABLE V. VALUES OF FLEXURAL STRENGTH

Sl. No	Mix	Flexural Strength (MPa)		
		7 Days	14 days	28 Days
1	Referenced Concrete	2.8	3.52	4.03
2	Mix-1	2.55	3.23	3.63
3	Mix-2	2.32	2.91	3.37
4	Mix-3	2.02	2.47	2.83
5	Mix-4	1.72	2.01	2.44

Fig. 7. Flexural Strength for 7 Days, 14 Days and 28 Days

CONCLUSIONS

1. Adding Groundnut Shell powder reduces the strength of the concrete for compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength.
2. After 7, 14 and 28 days of curing the concrete does not gain any strength at any percentage.
3. It happens due to material properties and chemical reactions formed between the components of concrete.
4. Due to the addition of groundnut shell powder there is decrease in the strength of the concrete to counteract this we need to be add admixtures like superplasticizers or chemical reagents, etc.(e.g., Calcium nitrate, Polycarboxylate Ether).
5. As we have observed the strength of the concrete is approximately similar to the nominal strength of the concrete at 2.5% replacement of groundnut shell powder. So, a groundnut shell will be useful upto 2.5% for the replacement of cement.

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